

TRACING THE HISTORY OF ISLAM IN DKI JAKARTA THROUGH RELIGIOUS TOURISM

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Abstract

There is a mixing of ethnic, tribe and nation form the people of DKI Jakarta. Of all the mixing available, Islamic teachings tend to be dominant in various aspects. This article attempts to trace Islam in DKI Jakarta through religious tourism in DKI Jakarta; by mapping and analyzing the lives of ulama/community leaders, whose tombs are widely visited. From the results obtained, is expected to be a trailer for visitors to get to know the characters visited, as well as to know the development of Islam in Jakarta.

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1. Introduction

Before Islam entered Indonesia, people in general still embraced Hinduism. Merchants from Arabia brought Islam into Indonesia, and the first time Islam was present in Aceh. They came not only to do business but also to spread Islam. The merchants landed their merchant ships on the coast.

The walisongo pioneered early conversion to Islam in Java. In West Java, it was directly distributed by one of the walisongo namely Sunan Gunung Jati, the son of Nyai Rarasantang. Nyai Rarasantang, son of Raden Pamanahrasa or Prabu Siliwangi who married Nyi Mas Subanglarang santri of Quro Shaykh from Karawang.

At the age of 20, Sunan Gunung Jati was determined to spread Islam and refused to become king of Egypt. In 1470 AD he arrived at Caruban to meet his mother Prince Walangsungsang who later was appointed as an educator or teacher at the *pesantren*. When Syarif Hidayatullah (Sunan Gunung Jati) visited Banten and spread Islam, he was able to Islamize the Regent of Kawunganten and his followers. Besides that, he also married his daughter, Nyi Mas Kawunganten. From the marriage, there were two sons, Sabakingkin (Sultan Hasanudin) and Ratu Winaon. By Sunan Gunung Jati, Banten was used as the center for the spread of Islam which was entrusted to Sultan Hasanudin, his son with the area of distribution including South Banten, Sunda Kelapa, Bogor, and Sukabumi²⁵.

Jakarta, which is currently the capital city of the country, is a sophisticated city, inhabited by various kinds of adherents of existing beliefs and different ethnic groups. Their arrival aims to work, entrepreneurship or entrepreneurship, considering that in Indonesia's several religions have been legalized as official religions, such as Islam, Catholicism, Catholicism, Protestantism,

²⁵ Teguh Asmar, *Sejarah Jawa Barat, dari masa Pra Sejarah Hingga Masa Penyebaran Agama Islam*. (Bandung: Proyek Penunjang Peningkatan Kebudayaan Nasional Propinsi Jawa Barat, 1975) p 97.

Hinduism, Buddhism, and Confucianism. Of these religions, Islam is the majority religion, including in Jakarta²⁶.

As a whole, Islam began to appear in Jakarta when Sunda Kelapa was controlled by Fatahillah and changed its name to Jayakarta. At that time the Islamic government in Jayakarta was very advanced. However, the triumph of Islam in Jayakarta did not last long and only lasted around 92 years. Furthermore, Jayakarta was conquered by the Dutch.

When Jayakarta surrendered to the Dutch, and its name changed to Batavia. Sultan Agung, who wanted to restore the honor of the Javanese who spread Islam in Betawi, then carried out an attack which resulted in the Mataram - Dutch war. The war itself was a failure, but it was Islam which had been spread for more than 92 years under the Banten sultanate under the name Jayakarta palace. It turned out to leave traces of its own. This study discusses how to know the traces of Islamic history that were once present in Jakarta through tombs and mosques.

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach, literature study and field study where researchers try to dig up as much information as possible about the issues that become the research topic by prioritizing the data obtained from the literature study and adjusting it to the events in the field by interviewing and observation.

Library study is the first step in data collection methods. Literature study is a method of data collection directed to the search for data and information through documents, both written documents, photographs, pictures, and electronic documents that can support the writing process. "The results of the study will also be more credible if supported by photographs or academic and art writings that already exist²⁷.

The instruments in this study were observations of religious tourism areas in Jakarta and also interviews with *Kuncen* to validate the data obtained through a literature study. The tombs in the area of Jakarta include the Luar Batang sacred grave, the sacred grave of Kampung Bandan, the Keramat Tomb of Pangeran Jayakarta, the Angke Holy Graveyard, and old mosques in Jakarta.

2. Discussion

Regarding the beginning of the spread of Islam in Jakarta, there were two opinions. The first according to Ridwan Saidi, the beginning of the spread of Islam in Jakarta can be followed by the establishment of the Quro Islamic Boarding School in 1491 AD in Karawang. Quro Shaykh is Syekh Hasanudin a Cambodian; he came to Java to preach, he landed his ship in Karawang and built a pesantren. During his leadership in the pesantren, he had many students, one of whom was named Nyai Subang Larang which was later edited by King Siliwangi. Besides that Sheikh Quro also built a mosque. According to Ridwan Saidi, since the Quro Shaykh founded the pesantren, the spread of Islam among the population experienced development²⁸.

In the second opinion, the presence of Islam in Jakarta began when the city was still called Sunda Kelapa and then controlled by Fatahillah on June 22, 1527 AD and gave a new name namely "Jayakarta" which means Pure Victory²⁹. The name was inspired by the verse of the Qur'an Inna Fatahna Laka Fathan Mubina (Surah al Fatah, verse 1) and the victory of the

²⁶ H. Ridwan Saidi, *Babad Tanah Betawi*, (Jakarta: Gria Media Prima, 2002) hal.109.

²⁷ Sugiyono, *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. (Bandung: Alfabeta,2005) hal.83.

²⁸ H.Ridwan Saidi Op.Cit hal.109

²⁹ Soekanto, *Dari Djakarta ke Djajakarta*, (Djakarta : Penerbit Soeroengan, 1954) p 60.

Messenger of Allah over Makkah in the month of Ramadan 8 Hijri / January 630. Fatahilah was the first Muslim army to conquer Banten and then control Sunda Kelapa from Padjajaran in 1527³⁰.

The Islamic government began when Fatahillah ruled Sunda Kelapa then given the name Jayakarta on June 22, 1527. Since Fatahillah was appointed by Sunan Gunung Jati to become the first reagent, he ruled until 1570, and then Tubagus Angke became ruler in Jayakarta from 1570 to 1596 and since 1596 Prince Jayakarta Wijayakrama became ruler in Jayakarta until 30 May 1619 AD. During his tenure as a ruler in Jayakarta, Pangeran Jayakarta also had a city pattern like other Islamic cities in Java. For religious activities, the mosque is in the middle of the city and used as a place for the spread of Islam³¹.

Then the triumph of the Islamic empire in Jayakarta ended when the Dutch VOC conquered Jayakarta and subsequently the city of Jayakarta and the palace of Pangeran Jayakarta and the mosque were burned and controlled by J.P. Coen, the General Governor of the VOC and renamed Jayakarta to Batavia as the Dutch colonial center in Indonesia until 1942³².

When the Dutch colonial ruled Jakarta (when it was named Batavia), Muslims were expected to retreat inland. The target areas include East Sunter River to Jatinegara Kaum, where they established the Assalafiyah Mosque in 1620. The mosque as the center of Islamic religious activities, in the 17th century, was located in Jatinegara, not in the center of Batavia.

According to the research of mosques that have been established in the 17th century in Batavia is the As-Salafiyah Mosque established in 1620, Al-Atiq Mosque in 1630 in Kampung Melayu, Al-Alam Mosque in 1655 in Cilincing and Alam Mosque in Marunda and Cilincing in 1663. The fact proves that the Islamic community does not deal directly with the Dutch³³. Because at that time the Dutch Government banned the construction of mosques both outside especially inside the walls of Batavia³⁴.

However, the ban on mosque construction loosened so that the development of Islam in Batavia in the 18th century expanded. In North Batavia in 1789 stood the Kampung Bandan Mosque and Luar Batang Mosque in 1735, the Pakojan Mosque in 1760. In the western part of Batavia, the Kebo Jeruk mosque was established in 1718, the Angke Mosque in 1761, al Mansur Mosque in 1717 and Tambora Mosque in 1762, Al-Makmur Mosque in Tanah Abang in 1760³⁵.

Starting from the religion of Islam in Batavia continues to grow. The strong influence of Islam and anti-Western sentiments in the mid-19th century can be caused by the increasing development of Islamic da'wah, especially with the emergence of some prominent scholars and habaib. So when the Dutch government took control of Batavia until 1942, the indigenous population remained Muslim.

However, interestingly, from all that there is no authentic Islamic heritage in Jakarta, for example, the Jayakarta Palace only leaves the tombs that are frequently visited, and mosques

³⁰ R. Soekmono, *Pengantar Sejarah Kebudayaan Indonesia*, jilid ke-3, (Yogyakarta : Kanisius, 1973) hal.56

³¹ M. Dien Majid, *Berhaji di Masa Kolonial*, (Jakarta: CV. Sejahtera, 2008) hal.84

³² Ahmda Fadhli, *Ulama Betawi (Studi Tentang Jaringan Ulama Betawi dan Kontribusinya Terhadap Perkembangan Islam Abad ke-19 dan 20)*. (Jakarta : Manhalun Nasyi-in Press, 2011) hal.45.

³³ Tim Peneliti, *Sejarah Perkembangan Islam di Jakarta, Abad XVII sampai Abad XX*, Fakultas Adab IAIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta, hal 20.

³⁴ *Ibid*, hal 87.

³⁵ A. Heuken SJ, *Mesjid-mesjid Tua di Jakarta*. (Jakarta : Yayasan Cipta Loka Caraka, 2003) hal. 43-71.

visited. Therefore, with the existence of graves and old mosques can be evidence and history lessons that Islam in Jakarta has existed since time immemorial around the 16th century. So, the number of old mosques and tombs indicates that the place is an Islamic area.

Figure 1. Map of Spreadi of Islam in Jakarta 16th century to 20th century

The picture above is an illustrated map of the spread of Islam in Jakarta through tombs and mosques from the 16th century to the 20th century. In the 19th and 20th centuries, the construction of mosques was no longer disturbed by the Dutch colonial government. So many mosques and prayer rooms were built. Therefore, only a few mosques and tombs are included, namely those that have historical and social backgrounds. The spread of Islam in Jakarta starting from the 16th century until now Islamic da'wah has an unbroken relay of Islamic struggle. Evidenced by the existence of graves and mosques in each generation and can be used as learning by presenting authentic evidence of the spread of Islam in Jakarta.

According to the general Indonesian dictionary, history can be interpreted as genealogy, origin (descent), or events that occurred in the past. Whereas according to Sartono Kartodirdjo, history is an illustration of the past of man and its surroundings as social beings that are compiled wholly and scientifically. Includes a sequence of facts of the period with interpretations and explanations that provide an understanding of what has passed³⁶. With the history of learning, it can help in understanding human behavior in the past, present, and future. People will not learn history if there is no benefit. The fact that history continues to be written by people in all civilizations and throughout time is quite proof that history is necessary³⁷. In an academic context, history is a field of science or field of study that requires critical historical

³⁶ Kartodirdjo, Sartono, *Pemikiran Dan Perkembangan Historiografi Indonesia Suatu Alternatif*. (Jakarta : Gramedia, 1982) hal.12

³⁷ Kuntowijoyo, *Pengantar Ilmu Sejarah* (Yogyakarta: Yayasan Bintang Budaya, 1995). Hal.19

imagination in its study. History is according to Suyatno Kartodirdjo³⁸ intended to place history in a phenomenological historical setting.

History is a critical reasoning and careful work to find the truth, a reasonable explanation of the causes and origins of everything, in-depth knowledge of how and why these events occurred. History can teach man of action about how others act in exceptional circumstances, the choices they make, and about their successes and failures. Without knowing history, someone will lose direction and reference in carrying out his wisdom³⁹. Because history is a bridge between the past and the present, and as a direction for the future⁴⁰. So it can be concluded that history is the study of events or events in the human past and reconstructs what happened in the past and can provide current and future effects.

Therefore, many people are flocking to religious tourism to ancient tombs or mosques in Jakarta. According to Suryono, religious tourism is interpreted as a tourism activity to a place that has a special meaning, the places commonly visited in religious tourism, including mosques, as a religious center where the mosque is used to pray, *i'tikaf*, *adzan* and *iqama*. Then, the tomb in the Javanese tradition, a place that contains sacredness. The tomb in Javanese is a higher name (respect) *cesarean*, a noun that comes from and *sare*, (sleep). In the traditional view, a tomb is a resting place⁴¹.

In particular, the function of a tomb is closely related to the pilgrimage ritual. Pilgrimage is one of the practices of most religious people who have essential moral meaning. Sometimes pilgrimages are made to a sacred place for the faith and faith concerned. The goal is to recall, strengthen faith or purify oneself. People who make this trip are called pilgrims. Pilgrimage is carried out to places that are considered to have spiritual and sacred values so that they are considered to influence increasing the level of one's spirituality. In the archipelago, a pilgrimage that is mostly carried out by traditionalist Muslims is usually made in sacred tombs, places of *petilasan* or place of residence of someone who is considered significant and influential⁴². Pilgrimage tourism is a type of tourism which is more or less associated with religion, history, customs and beliefs of people or groups in society. Individuals or groups can do pilgrimage tours in the holy place, the graves of significant people, leaders who are glorified, to the hill or mountain that are considered sacred, burial of figures or leaders as magical people full of legends announced by Nyoman S.Pendit⁴³. So religious tourism can be divided into two, namely religious tourism grave pilgrimage and mosque religious tourism. Religious tourism is a grave pilgrimage such as the Keramat Luar Batang, the Keramat Angke Tomb, the Tomb of Prince Jayakarta, the Sacred Tomb of Kampung Bandan and others. While religious tourism of

³⁸ Suyatno Kartodirdjo, "Teori dan Metodologi Sejarah dalam Aplikasinya", dalam *Historika*, No. 11 Tahun XII. (Surakarta: Program Pasca Sarjana Universitas Negeri Jakarta KPK Universitas Sebelas Maret Surakarta, 2000). hal. 31

³⁹ Ahmad Maksum, *Interprestasi Sejarah sebagai Peristiwa dan Masalah Pendidikan*, At Turats Vol.9 No.2 Desember 2015, Hal.6

⁴⁰ Ahmad Syafii Maarif, *Keterkaitan Antara Sejarah, Filsafat, dan Agama* (Yogyakarta: IKIP Yogyakarta, 1997). p.4

⁴¹ Mustika, *skripsi : Pengelolaan Wisata Religi; Studi Kasus Makam Sultan Hadiwijaya Untuk Pengembangan Dakwah*. (Semarang: Institut Agama Islam Walisongo, 2011) hal.33

⁴² Henri Chambert Loir dan Claude Guillot, *Ziarah & Wali di Dunia Islam*, Depok: Komunitas Bambu, 2010. p.333

⁴³ Nyoman S.Pendit, *Ilmu Pariwisata Sebuah Pengantar Perdana*. (Jakarta: PT. Pradnya Paramita,2002). pp.42.

mosques such as Istiqlal Mosque, Al Anwar Mosque, Masjid As Salafiyah, and others. Religious tourism can also improve spirituality and change attitudes to others after many religious tourism visits⁴⁴.

Furthermore, at this time the form of religious tourism can not only see or make a pilgrimage to a mosque or graveyard but rather something that can be done such as recitation. Besides that, religious tourism can be a suggestion in learning Islamic history in Jakarta.

From religious tourism activities when looking at the age of a tomb or mosque, it can determine the length of Islam that was ever present in Jakarta. For example, a site in Kampung Bandan that mentions the person who was buried in 1705 namely the tomb of Sayyid Moh. Bin Umar al-Qudsi, it was estimated that Islam had existed for a long time in that area before 1705 ago⁴⁵. Assuming he came, there was already an established Islamic community That was proven by the capture of Sunda Kelapa by Fatahillah in 1527 and changed it to Jayakarta. Starting from where Islam developed rapidly, the site that proves Islam has existed since the 16th century is the tomb of Prince Tubagus Angke around the Angke Mosque.

When Prince Ahmad Jayakarta led Jayakarta, it was later conquered by the Dutch who eventually fled to Jatinegara kaum area in 1619⁴⁶. However, with the site in Kampung Bandan, the tomb of Sayyid Moh. Bin Umar al-Qudsi showed the relay of the ulama struggle in Jakarta. Moreover, the location of the graves scattered in many places and the order of death of the people who are buried shows that the generation of scholars continues to grow even though there are scholars who die. There is a relay of the Islamization struggle in Jakarta that has never gone extinct. What is meant by Islamization here is to fight for and defend the existing Islam.

Islamization is divided into two, namely first to Islamize people who have not entered Islam and the second is to maintain and preserve the existing Islam or maintain Islamic da'wah in that location. Because if it is not guarded and guarded, it will be persuaded by the persuasion of the Dutch government because at that time the Dutch government was incessantly carrying out missionary practices so that Muslims adhered to their religion. So the understanding of Islamization must be distinguished.

With religious tourism can see that Islam in Jakarta has a relay of struggle according to an uninterrupted time. Some generations die, and some generations continue to be connected to each other who have a clear sanad. From religious tourism, it does not only come to people who are dead. However, it can revive the traces of people who have died when they live. Because people who have died have lived and they are remembered for their exemplary lives. So the tomb included authentic evidence in the spread of Islam in Jakarta.

The fact behind the silent tombs is that there is an Islamic story present in the Jakarta community. Because the tomb does not only talk about people, who are dead. However, the tomb is a legacy of living people which makes it authentic evidence of the spread of Islam in Jakarta.

Currently, religious tourism is in high demand by many tourists. Religious tourism can be observed by looking at the many people who make pilgrimages to the guardian tombs, ulama, and kyai who are considered to have certain karomah, such as visiting the tombs or mosques of

⁴⁴ Khumaeroh, Umi; Sari Narulita & Rihlah Nur Aulia. "*The Improvement of Intrapersonal Communication Through Religious Tourism*" UUM Malaysia: Proceedings International Conference on Media Studies, 2017, pp 419 - 425

⁴⁵ A.Heuken SJ, op,cit. hal.70

⁴⁶ Lasmiyati, *Penyebaran Agama Islam di Jakarta Abad XVII-XIX*. Patanjala. Vol.1 No.1, Maret 2009, pp 79.

the history of Islam in Jakarta. So enthusiastic about the community to visit or visit the graves of guardians in Jakarta.

However, it is unfortunate that the management of religious tourism places in Jakarta, especially the tombs is not adequate, such as facilities and infrastructure. In addition what is more, necessary is the information about religious tourism places, there are no explanations around the tomb or mosque about the place, if want more in-depth information, meet the critical juror (kuncen) or the mentor of the religious tourism group. Researchers hope that in the future religious attractions can provide information around the place such as the presence of making or writings around the tomb or mosque about the history and struggle of Islam. So that these religious attractions can genuinely be a means for more effective history learning because of plunging directly into authentic evidence

3. Conclusion

Islam in Jakarta began to appear when the city was still named Sunda Kelapa and then controlled by Fatahillah on June 22, 1527 AD and gave a new name namely "Jayakarta" which means Pure Victory. The triumph of the Islamic empire in Jayakarta ended when the Dutch VOC conquered Jayakarta and subsequently the city of Jayakarta and the palace of Pangeran Jayakarta and the mosque were burned and controlled by J.P. Coen, the General Governor of the VOC and changed its name from Jayakarta to Batavia as the Dutch colonial center in Indonesia until 1942. The triumph of Islam in Jayakarta did not last long and only lasted around 92 years.

Interestingly, of all that there was no authentic Islamic heritage in Jakarta, for example, the Jayakarta Palace only left the tombs that were frequently visited, and mosques visited. Therefore, the existence of graves and old mosques can be evidence and history lessons that Islam in Jakarta has existed since time immemorial around the 16th century. So, the number of old mosques and tombs indicates that the place is an Islamic area.

History is important in life because history is a link between the past and the present, and as a direction for the future. The history of Islam in Jakarta can be known through relics such as tombs and mosques. Many people in Jakarta do religious tourism either to mosques or graves.

With religious tourism it can be seen that Islam in Jakarta has a relay of struggle according to an uninterrupted time. Some generations die, and some generations continue to be connected to each other who have a clear sanad. From religious tourism, it does not only come to people who are dead. However, it can revive the traces of people who have died when they live. Because people who have died have lived and they are remembered for their exemplary lives. So the tomb included authentic evidence in the spread of Islam in Jakarta.

However, until now these religious attractions have not been arranged neatly, there are still many inadequate facilities and infrastructure. Moreover, information on religious tourism still lacks in explanations about religious tourist attractions, so many visitors do not know. The tombs and mosques are authentic evidence of the spread of Islam in Jakarta which can be used as a linear history of learning.

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